

**Ministry of Higher
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**Al-Kitab University
College of Nursing**

Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital

A project submitted
by:

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To:

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بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ

﴿يُؤْتِي الْحِكْمَةَ مَنْ يَشَاءُ وَمَنْ يُؤْتَ الْحِكْمَةَ فَقَدْ أُوتِيَ

خَيْرًا كَثِيرًا وَمَا يَذَّكَّرُ إِلَّا أُولُو الْأَلْبَابِ﴾

[البقرة: 269]

Committee Certification

We are the members of the examining committee; certify that after reading the projected entitled (Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital) and examining the students in its contents, it is adequate for the award of the Bachelor's Degree of Nursing Sciences.

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I certify that this project was prepared under my supervision at the College of Nursing, University of Al-Kitab in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Bachelor's Degree of Nursing Sciences.

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Abstract

Background: Artificial intelligence is a science concerned with simulating human cognitive abilities through complex algorithms and has the full potential to make a major transformation in the field of nursing practice.

Goals: This study aims to assess nurses' knowledge and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital and to determine nurses' knowledge and attitudes according to their demographic characteristics.

Methodology: This study adopted a descriptive quantitative design. The study was conducted between November 10, 2025, and March 15, 2026, and a non-probability (purposive) sample of 40 nurses working at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital was selected. The questionnaire consists of three parts: the first includes the demographic characteristics of the participants, the second includes the nurses' knowledge, and the third includes the nurses' attitudes towards AI. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages).

Conclusions: The study concluded that the majority of nurses demonstrated moderate knowledge and neutral attitudes towards the use of AI tools. It also showed that most of nurses are females with less than 5 years of experience and who hold a nursing diploma. It also showed that nearly all of them had not received any education or training courses on AI.

Recommendations: The study recommends enhancing continuous education on AI tools and ethics within the Kirkuk Health Directorate, integrating AI into nursing curricula, specifically at Al-Kitab University, emphasizing its potential for social good, and expanding future research through larger, more diverse samples.

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List of Abbreviation

Abbr.	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
<i>f</i>	Frequency
n	Number

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence, commonly referred to as AI, is the science of making intelligent computer programs that produce intelligent tools aimed at understanding and simulating human cognitive abilities (McCarthy, 2007).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming a variety of healthcare-related domains. Artificial intelligence (AI) has always occupied the minds of nurses with regard to its various tools, as it has interconnected with healthcare from many aspects. Furthermore, its capabilities are fuelled by data, it provides personalised treatment recommendations, assists nurses as an aid for real-time monitoring, and presents support and education through virtual assistant chatbots, predictive models for disease progression, patient stratification, as well as additional applications within the context of healthcare (Li *et al.*, 2024).

Furthermore, research have demonstrated that the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in nursing has the potential to significantly improve nursing care quality (Ng *et al.*, 2021; Rony *et al.*, 2025). In addition, this transformative role of artificial intelligence in nursing contributes to enhancing patient safety and minimising error rates (Mikkonen *et al.*, 2025).

In considering this technological advancement and the revolutionary transformation triggered by artificial intelligence in the field of nursing, it has been observed at the worldwide level that there is limited knowledge about artificial intelligence among nursing professionals. Regardless of this

fact, the worldwide landscape reflects a substantial majority of positive attitudes among nursing personnel (Sandanasamy *et al.*, 2025).

1.2 Importance of the study

Artificial intelligence has the potential to completely transform the field of nursing and have a significant impact on the quality of healthcare. By employing AI technology, nursing personnel can enhance patient care, make better decisions, streamline workflows, and improve how healthcare is delivered. It is predicted that artificial intelligence would contribute to proactive care and reduce future risks for patients, nurses, and the nursing field as a whole (Tursunbayeva and Renkema, 2022).

In addition, artificial intelligence has additionally demonstrated a role in promoting positive nursing practice environments and has demonstrated clear benefits for all aspects of the healthcare field (De Abreu Pereira *et al.*, 2025).

Furthermore, nursing professionals should take on major responsibilities as advocates and supporters of its safe and ethical implementation throughout the field of healthcare (Yakusheva, Bouvier and Hagopian, 2024).

1.3 Objective of the study

1. To assess nurses' knowledge towards the use of artificial intelligence tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital.
2. To assess nurses' attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital

3. To determine nurses' knowledge and attitudes according to their demographic characteristics.

1.4 Statement of the problem

Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital.

1.5 Definition of Terms

1.5.1 Nurse:

Theoretical Definition:

A nurse is a professional who is qualified to practice nursing based on established standards of practice and ethical guidelines. They are also educated in the scientific knowledge, skills, and philosophy of nursing (International Council of Nurses, n.d.).

Operational Definition:

A healthcare provider collaborates with other professionals to prevent illness, help alleviate suffering, and promote optimal health for individuals, families, communities, and populations.

1.5.2 Artificial Intelligence:

Theoretical Definition:

the ability of a machine to perform cognitive functions associated with human cognitive abilities, such as perceiving, reasoning, learning,

interacting with the environment, problem solving, decision-making, and perhaps even demonstrating creativity (Kühl *et al.*, 2022).

Operational Definition:

Artificial intelligence is a technology that allows computers and machines to approximate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision-making, creativity, and autonomy.

1.5.3 Knowledge:**Theoretical Definition:**

It is the capacity to acquire, retain and use material, a mixture of understanding, experience and skills (The Analysis of Knowledge (Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy), 2026).

Operational Definition:

The degree to which the nurses perceived principles and information concerning the use of artificial intelligence tools.

1.5.4 Attitudes:**Theoretical Definition:**

The pattern of feelings, beliefs, and reactions that an individual holds regarding particular people, objects, or ideas and are often formed based on an individual's past experience (APA Dictionary of Psychology, no date).

Operational Definition:

Nurses' feelings or opinions or behaviours towards the use of artificial intelligence tools.

CHAPTER TWO
LITERATURE
REVIEW

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Historical Background

The expression "artificial intelligence" (AI) is defined as the use of a computer to simulate intelligent behaviour with minimal assistance coming from a human, it is generally agreed upon that the creation of robots was the beginning of artificial intelligence (Hamet and Tremblay, 2017).

This concept began with Alan Turing in 1950, who in turn performed a simple test called the "Turing test" to evaluate the possibility that computers would be capable of demonstrating human intelligence. Six years later, John McCarthy defined the term artificial intelligence (AI) as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines." (Kaul, Enslin and Gross, 2020).

In the decade of the seventies, AI with established medical applications started to develop interest. In 1971, the first artificial medical consultant in history, INTERNIST-1, was developed. Based on the symptoms of the patients, the system produced clinical diagnoses based on a search algorithm. Due to INTERNIST-1 offered a way for health care professionals to verify the accuracy of their differential diagnoses and had a clear ability to relieve some of the burden of clinical diagnosis from healthcare providers, it led to a major transformation in AI in clinical research. By the present moment, it was clear to see that artificial intelligence (AI) had many potential applications in the healthcare field. The following significant advancement occurred at the University of Massachusetts in the 1980s. A program called DXplain was developed to assist medical professionals in making diagnoses. A possible diagnosis would be coming back by the system when clinicians entered symptoms. identical to INTERNIST-1, the system increased the number of

clinical diagnoses it could produce and gave healthcare professionals accessibility to an early information database for current health information. Then the early 2000s was the beginning of the modern era of artificial intelligence (AI), which experienced some of the most significant advancements in applications of artificial intelligence to normal daily life and healthcare in general (Hirani *et al.*, 2024).

2.2 Application of Artificial Intelligence in Nursing Practice

The wider range of AI applications and roles is not far from the practice of nursing, as studies have shown important applications related to fundamental health care practices (Ruksakulpiwat *et al.*, 2024).

2.2.1 Risk Identification

Risk identification has been defined as one of the most significant and essential uses of artificial intelligence (AI), where electronic health records (EHR) are analysed to identify the risk of hospital readmission among adult patients discharged from healthcare services, as indicated by the retrospective study by Brom *et al.* (2019).

2.2.2 Health Assessment

The health assessment is perceived as an evident use of artificial intelligence, where AI has assisted nurses in diagnosing particular health issues. This demonstrates the effectiveness of AI-based tools assisting nurses (Jain *et al.*, 2021).

2.2.3 Developing a Nursing Care Plan

In general, artificial intelligence was utilised by nurses to assist in developing nursing care plans (Woodnutt *et al.*, 2023).

2.2.4 Research Development

Nursing professionals used artificial intelligence algorithms in developing scientific research, and practical recommendations were provided for nursing researchers who are interested in studies that are interdisciplinary (Fritz and Dermody, 2018).

2.2.5 Improved Care Delivery and Medical Record

A wide variety of valuable consequences are demonstrated by the current evaluation of artificial intelligence (AI) systems in the fields of healthcare and nursing, including increased access to high-quality health care, improvements in medical record management, and general increases in the quality of care. For the purpose to improve healthcare programs for increased efficacy and efficiency, these advantages highlight the benefits and critical need for integrating AI-based systems in healthcare (Pailaha, 2023).

2.3 Nurses' Knowledge regarding the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools and Related Factors

Across the globe, previous published research demonstrated a noticeable weakness in nurses' knowledge about tools and the concept of artificial intelligence among nurses (Sandanasamy *et al.*, 2025).

Research results have demonstrated the fact that there is a strong and significant relationship between nursing knowledge about the use of artificial intelligence and its tools, and the level of education, gender, and type of setting in which professionals in nursing practice their profession (Sommer, Schmidbauer and Wahl, 2024).

Higher-level educated nurses have a tendency towards being more knowledgeable about artificial intelligence (AI) and to have more positive attitudes toward it. In the present scenario, a German study demonstrates how important it is to integrate artificial intelligence-related subjects into both undergraduate and graduate nursing degree programs (Busch *et al.*, 2023).

A further factor influencing nurses' knowledge of artificial intelligence (AI) is the type of healthcare facility; nurses working in higher education institutions or facilities with advanced technologies had more exposure to artificial intelligence (AI) applications, which potentially contributed to their deeper knowledge of AI (Chikhaoui, Alajmi and Larabi-Marie-Sainte, 2022).

Nevertheless, at the local level, there is a lack of expertise and limited knowledge about artificial intelligence (AI), as previous literature has indicated, relating it to the primary barriers in Iraq: the lack of technological infrastructure, limited funding, and the need for specialised faculty training (Salimi *et al.*, 2025).

2.4 Nurses' Attitudes regarding the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools and Related Factors

The global nursing literature demonstrates modest optimism, Anxiety and demographics limited involvement, while perceived usefulness, self-efficacy, and supportive environments improve attitude. Strong governance and ethics, modernised infrastructure, continuous hands-on training, and integrating longitudinal AI competencies into educational programs are priorities (Arab *et al.*, 2025).

On the Iraqi level, nurses in a previous study involving hospitals in Hilla, Babil Governorate, demonstrated a positive attitude among 83.3% of the participating nurses (Khalil and Yasir, 2025).

2.5 Study Originality and Research Gap

After reviewing the previous literature, it is quite understood that there is a global nursing interest in assessing nurses' knowledge and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence.

Although, on a national level, there is a serious lack of research in this regard. Despite the existence of a single study on the same area of study performed in Babil Governorate by researchers Khalil and Yasir (2025), its results remain restricted to its geographical context. Another study in the city of Kirkuk included healthcare professionals but only involved 6 nurses, performed by Bakr (2025), which of course cannot be generalised to the hospitals of Kirkuk Governorate, especially the Kirkuk Teaching Hospital.

Consequently, the originality of this study emerges as it is the first of its kind locally, aiming to provide a foundational database that could benefit researchers, nurses, and nursing as a whole.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

Chapter Three: Methodology

This chapter utilises the following to represent the study's methodology:

3.1 Design of the Study

This quantitative descriptive study has been conducted at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital in Kirkuk Governorate from November 10, 2025, to March 15, 2026, in order to assess nurses' attitudes and knowledge towards the use of artificial intelligence tools using a questionnaire-based assessment methodology.

3.2 Administrative Arrangements

Permission had been granted from the College of Nursing, Al-Kitab University and the Kirkuk Health Directorate before the data was actually compiled (Appendix A1, A2). Participation was voluntary, and all participants provided implied informed consent by completing the questionnaire.

3.3 Settings of the Study

The study was conducted at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital in the Kirkuk Governorate.

3.4 Study Sample

A purposive (non-probability) sample is selected for the purpose of study which includes forty (40) nurses. The sample is selected from nurses that work at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital included during this study.

3.5.1 The Study Instrument

In order to assess the nurses' knowledge and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools at Kirkuk teaching hospital, the researchers designed a questionnaire. The study's complete instrument is divided into three sections (Appendix B):

Part 1: Includes demographic data about nurses, such as gender, age, marital status, years of experience, education level, department or ward, prior AI training, course duration, and location.

Part 2: The assessment questionnaire of knowledge towards the use of AI tools is divided into three sections and consists of (12) closed-ended questions based on previous studies, a review of the literature, and the background of the researchers. There was a sufficient amount of time for all participants to respond to the questions.

Part 3: The assessment questionnaire of attitudes towards the use of AI tools is divided into four sections and consists of (14) closed-ended questions based on what the previous sections of this questionnaire were based on.

3.5.2 Rating and Scoring

The items of questionnaire have received ratings and scores according to the following patterns:

1. The nurses' knowledge in each question was evaluated using a three-point Likert scale, and the possible answers for each item were determined as follows: (1) for "I don't know", (2) for "not sure" and (3) for "I know". High scores for

assessing nurses' knowledge regarding the use of artificial intelligence tools indicate a high level of knowledge.

2. The nurses' attitudes to each question were assessed using a five-point Likert scale, with the possible responses for each item defined as follows: (5) "Strongly agree", (4) "Agree", (3) "Not sure", (2) "Disagree", and (1) "Strongly disagree". High scores of nurses' attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools indicate positive attitudes.

3.6 Validity of the Questionnaire

The validity of the questionnaire was verified by a panel composed of five experts with over 10 years of experience (Appendix C). These experts were faculty members (5) from the College of Nursing and the College of Technical Engineering at Al-Kitab University.

3.7 Data Collection

Data had been collected through the application of the questionnaire, which was prepared with the help of structured interviews. They were interviewed individually in the wards and departments of Kirkuk Teaching Hospital, using the Arabic version of the questionnaire with an oral explanation of the questions in the local languages, using the same questionnaire with all the nurses included in the study sample. The interview takes no less than 10 minutes for each participant.

3.8 Reliability of the Questionnaire

The scale's Cronbach alpha correlation coefficient is calculated to evaluate internal consistency reliability. For the entire questionnaire, the scale's internal reliability has been determined to be (0.76) for 26 items. This value indicates that the instrument demonstrates a good level of internal consistency, as it meets or exceeds the generally accepted statistical threshold of (0.70).

3.9 Statistical Data Analysis

The data in this study are analysed using statistical techniques, Microsoft Excel, and SPSS version 26 to interpret the results of the research.

3.10 Descriptive statistical procedure

The following methods were used to analyse the data:

- 1- Frequency (*f*).
- 2- Percentage (%).

3.11 Study limitations:

The present study dealt with multiple limitations. First, the time restrictions, such as data collection was limited to a specific period during the academic year (2025-2026). Secondly, the spatial limitations, as the study was conducted at the Kirkuk Teaching Hospital, which in turn limits the number of participants and affects the possibility of generalising the results on a national level and within Kirkuk Governorate. Furthermore, the excessive workload and time pressures faced by nurses during their shifts might cause a challenge in guaranteeing complete concentration while filling out the questionnaire, as well as affecting the number of nurses participating in the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

Chapter Four: Results of the Study

This chapter presents the results of the study as follows:

Table 4-1: Frequencies and Percentages of Socio-Demographical Characteristics (n=40).

Socio-Demographical Characteristics		<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	17	42.5
	Female	23	57.5
Age	20-29 Years	34	85.0
	30-39 Years	3	7.5
	40-49 Years	1	2.5
	50-59 Years	2	5.0
Level of Education	Preparatory School Certificate	2	5.0
	Diploma Degree	23	57.5
	Bachelor's Degree	15	37.5
Marital Status	Single	24	60.0
	Married	16	40.0
Years of Experience	less of 5	29	72.5
	5-9	8	20.0
	10-14	1	2.5
	15-19	0	0.0
	20-24	0	0.0
	25 and above	2	5.0
Department	A&E	12	30.0
	ICUCCU	9	22.5
	Medical	7	17.5
	Surgical	6	15.0
	Paediatric	3	7.5
	Gynaecology	2	5.0

	Other	1	2.5
Prior Training Course	Yes	2	5.0
	No	38	95.0

This table demonstrated the percentages of socio-demographical characteristics for study sample. Most samples were female 57.5% and 85.0% of all with age group between 20-29 years. And the majority of the participants are holders of a diploma in nursing, forming 57.5%. Regarding marital status, 60% of the participants were married. 72.5% of the sample worked for a duration of less than five years. The table demonstrates that 30% of the nurses in this study work in the emergency department. Only 5% of the nurses in this study participated in a training course on artificial intelligence (AI) that lasted between 3-5 days within the city of Kirkuk.

Table 4-2: Frequency and percentage of the Sample Knowledge level towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools.

General Knowledge Level	<i>f</i>	%
Poor (12-21)	1	2.5
Moderate (22-33)	21	52.5
High (31-36)	18	45.0

This table demonstrated that 45% of the study sample had a high level of knowledge, while 52.5% had a moderate level.

Table 4-3: Nurses' Knowledge level of sample towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools according to Socio-Demographical Characteristics.

Socio-Demographical Characteristics		Knowledge Level					
		Poor		Moderate		High	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	0	0.0	6	28.6	11	61.1
	Female	1	100.0	15	71.4	7	38.9
Age	20-29 Years	1	100.0	17	81.0	16	88.9
	30-39 Years	0	0.0	2	9.5	1	5.6
	40-49 Years	0	0.0	1	4.8	0	0.0
	50-59 Years	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	5.6
Level of Education	Preparatory School	0	0.0	1	4.8	1	5.6
	Diploma Degree	1	100.0	12	57.1	10	55.6
	Bachelor's Degree	0	0.0	8	38.1	7	38.9
Marital Status	Single	1	100.0	10	47.6	13	72.2
	Married	0	0.0	11	52.4	5	27.8
Years of Experience	less of 5	0	0.0	13	61.9	16	88.9
	5-9	1	100.0	5	23.8	2	11.1
	10-14	0	0.0	1	4.8	0	0.0
	15-19	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	20-24	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	25 and above	0	0.0	2	9.5	0	0.0
Department	A&E	0	0.0	8	38.1	4	22.2
	ICU\CCU	0	0.0	5	23.8	4	22.2
	Medical	0	0.0	2	9.5	5	27.8
	Surgical	0	0.0	2	9.5	4	22.2
	Paediatric	1	100.0	1	4.8	1	5.6
	Gynaecology	0	0.0	2	9.5	0	0.0
	Other	0	0.0	1	4.8	0	0.0

Prior AI Training Course	Yes	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	11.1
	No	1	100.0	21	100.0	16	88.9

This table demonstrates that the majority of the sample respondents are classified into the categories of moderate knowledge with 21 participants and high knowledge with 18 participants. While the poor knowledge category documented only one case, and that case was a female. The highest percentage of high knowledge was documented among the age group 20-29 years at 88.9% and among singles at 72.2%. It was also clearly noticed that nurses with less professional experience (less than 5 years) have the highest knowledge at 88.9%. It was found that diploma holders comprise the largest part in the high knowledge level at 57.1% and moderate knowledge level at 55.6%, subsequently being followed by bachelor's degree holders. Regarding prior training, the majority with high knowledge (88.9%) and moderately knowledge (100%) had not received any previous training courses on artificial intelligence (AI).

Table 4-4: Nurses' General Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools.

Nurses' General Attitudes	<i>f</i>	%
Negative (14-32)	1	2.5
Neutral (33-51)	32	80.0
Positive (52-70)	7	17.5

This table highlights the general attitudes of the study sample, where the overwhelming majority of participants demonstrated a neutral attitude, with 80% or 32 nurses participating.

Table 4-5: Nurses' Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools according to Socio-Demographical Characteristics.

Socio-Demographical Characteristics		Attitudes					
		Negative		Neutral		Positive	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	1	100.0	11	34.4	5	71.4
	Female	0	0.0	21	65.6	2	28.6
Age	20-29 Years	1	100.0	26	81.3	7	100.0
	30-39 Years	0	0.0	3	9.4	0	0.0
	40-49 Years	0	0.0	1	3.1	0	0.0
	50-59 Years	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0.0
Level of Education	Preparatory School	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0.0
	Diploma	1	100.0	17	53.1	5	71.4
	Bachelor's Degree	0	0.0	13	40.6	2	28.6
Marital Status	Single	1	100.0	18	56.3	5	71.4
	Married	0	0.0	14	43.8	2	28.6
Years of Experience	less of 5	1	100.0	22	68.8	6	85.7
	5-9	0	0.0	7	21.9	1	14.3
	10-14	0	0.0	1	3.1	0	0.0
	15-19	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	20-24	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	25 and above	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0.0
Department	A&E	0	0.0	8	25.0	4	57.1
	ICU\CCU	0	0.0	9	28.1	0	0.0
	Medical	1	100.0	4	12.5	2	28.6
	Surgical	0	0.0	6	18.8	0	0.0
	Paediatric	0	0.0	2	6.3	1	14.3
	Gynaecology	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0.0

	Other	0	0.0	1	3.1	0	0.0
Prior AI Training Course	Yes	0	0.0	2	6.3	0	0.0
	No	1	100.0	30	93.8	7	100.0

This table summarises nurses' attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools according to their demographic characteristics. Neutral attitudes were the largest part in the study, with nurses in the age group of 20-29 years showing a significant orientation towards neutral attitudes at a percentage of 81.3%. It was also noticed that the majority of participants with neutral attitudes hadn't been given any previous training courses (93.8%), and positive attitudes were mainly exclusive to the younger age group (20-29 years), with males significantly more common (71.4%) compared to females (28.6%). In addition, all those who demonstrated a positive attitude had not participated in any previous training courses. In terms of the negative attitudes, they were very limited in quantity (only one nurses), and was a male, single, within the age group (20-29 years), and had less than 5 years of experience. Regarding education and experience, diplomas were the most prevalent in all categories, while nurses with little professional experience (less than 5 years) were the most adequately represented in different categories.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Chapter Five: Discussion of the Results

This study described the knowledge and attitudes of nurses towards the use of artificial intelligence tools in Kirkuk Teaching Hospital, where the level of nurses' knowledge, especially their general knowledge about artificial intelligence as a concept and its applications in healthcare and nursing, and also about its limitations, was evaluated and described. Furthermore, the study focused on attitudes, concentrating on the expected benefits, professional concerns, ethics, privacy, human relationships, and the organisational readiness and acceptance of artificial intelligence within healthcare.

This study showed through **Table 4-1** that the majority of nurses in this study are female, representing 57.5%. This correlates with the global trend, where females occupy 70% of the healthcare workforce, with nurses summing up 89% of that percentage, according to the World Health Organization (2019), nursing remains a female-dominated field.

The table additionally demonstrated that the majority of the sample were aged between 20-29 years, resulting in 85% of the nurses in this study with a mean of 1.27. This corresponds to the study published by Khalil and Yasir (2025), where the sample was formed of participants aged 20-29 years, with a majority of 69.2%.

Our study concluded that 57.5% of nurses are graduates of nursing institutes and hold a diploma in nursing, followed by bachelor's degree holders at 37.5%. This is highly significant. Our study showed that 57.5% of the nurses are graduates of nursing institutes and hold a diploma in nursing, followed by bachelor's degree holders at 37.5%; this is significant, as Rony *et al.* (2024) that this same order was found throughout the sample, where diploma holders

represented 35.73% and thereafter were followed by bachelor's degree holders at 30.86%. Our study also found that the majority of nurses have fewer than five years of experience, which is 72.5% of the sample size, since they are considered the majority of the participants, followed by those with 5-9 years of experience at a percentage of 20%. And this is similar to the results of the study published by Abdelkareem, Bakri, and Ahmed (2024), where the majority of the sample had professional experience with no more than ten years. And according to this table, the majority of nurses were single, at 60%.

Table 4-1 and **Table 4-3** demonstrate that nearly all of the nurses, 95%, who participated in our study had not received any prior education or training course on artificial intelligence (AI). It is also important to note that most of the nurses who demonstrated high knowledge, 88.9%, and every single nurse who showed moderate knowledge did not receive any training course on AI, this is compatible with research published by Areshtanab *et al.* (2025), in which the percentage of nurses who hadn't completed any training on AI was 94.3%. And this may suggest that knowledge about artificial intelligence could be acquired or result from experience and is not related to programs and training courses.

Table 4-2 and **Table 4-8** demonstrate that greater than half of the nurses, at a percentage of 52.5% in this study, demonstrated moderate knowledge, followed by those who had high knowledge about AI at a percentage of 45.0%.

Table 4-3 concluded that the highest percentage of high knowledge was identified among the age group of 20-29 years at 88.9%, which reinforces the findings of the study by Alrashedi *et al.* (2026), where the study pointed out that younger nurses demonstrated considerably higher knowledge.

Table 4-4 demonstrated that the overwhelming majority of nurses, at a percentage of 80%, were in agreement on a neutral attitude towards the use of artificial intelligence tools. This disagrees with the study published by Khalil and Yasir (2025), which highlighted positive attitudes among nursing professionals.

Table 4-5 clarifies that the largest sample of nurses from all categories positions itself in a grey (neutral) spectrum regarding the use of artificial intelligence tools. This doesn't align well with the results of the study conducted by Rony, Kayesh, *et al.* (2024), which found that there is a positive attitude with cautious optimism towards the use of this technology, reflecting a need for targeted training programmes to ensure that nurses are adequately prepared to work effectively alongside artificial intelligence-based technologies. Training should not be limited to technical aspects only but should also include ethical considerations to enhance nurses' confidence in AI.

In conclusion, despite the small sample size of 40 nurses, the power of this study centres around being the first pioneering research move in Kirkuk Governorate and the second in Iraq in this vital discipline. Because of this, it provides a basic database that opens new horizons for researchers and health organisations to understand the readiness of nursing professionals for digital transformation, which makes it a cornerstone for more broad national studies in the future.

CHAPTER SIX
CONCLUSION &
RECOMMENDATIONS

Chapter Six: Conclusion & Recommendations**6.1 Conclusions**

Conclusions based on data analysis results and according to the objectives of this study:

- 1) Adult females between the ages of 20 and 29 constructed the majority of the staff working in nursing.
- 2) The educational level of the majority of nurses participating in this study was a diploma in nursing. With less than five years of professional experience for the majority of nurses.
- 3) A large proportion of nurses in this study, at 95% of the participants, had not previously participated in any training courses related to the use of artificial intelligence tools.
- 4) The general knowledge of nurses towards the use of artificial intelligence tools was moderate among 52.5% of the nurses and high among 45% of the nurses in this research study.
- 5) The study showed generally neutral attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools among the nurses in this study.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the study conclusion, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1) Enhancing continuous education and training in the Kirkuk Health Directorate towards the use of artificial intelligence tools in healthcare, with particular emphasis on the ethical considerations of the use of AI.
- 2) Encouraging nursing colleges, especially at Al-Kitab University, to provide training courses and workshops on the use of artificial intelligence tools and to incorporate AI as a core subject.
- 3) Artificial intelligence's potential for social good should be emphasised.
- 4) Emphasising the importance of conducting more research and including larger and more diverse samples on the use of artificial intelligence tools in nursing practice.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A1:

REPUBLIC OF IRAQ
MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION
AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH
AL-KITAB UNIVERSITY
College of Nursing

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
جامعة الكتاب
كلية التمريض

العدد : ١٧٤/٧

التاريخ : ٢٠٢٥/١٢/٣٠

الى / دائرة صحة كركوك / مركز التدريب والتنمية البشرية
م/ تسهيل مهمة

تحية طبية...

يرجى التفضل بالموافقة علي تسهيل مهمة طلبة المرحلة الرابعة في كليتنا لغرض انجاز بحوث التخرج للعام الدراسي (٢٠٢٥-٢٠٢٦) واكمال جمع العينات من مؤسساتكم الصحية بالقوائم المرفقة باسمااء الطلبة و عناوين بحوثهم.

المرفقات:-

١. قائمة باسمااء الطلبة المرحلة الرابعة

جامعة الكتاب
أ.م.د. ابراهيم حسين المنصفي
عميد كلية التمريض
٢٠٢٥/١٢/٣٠

نسخة منه الي:-

- مكتب السيد رئيس الجامعة.. للتفضل بالاطلاع.. مع التقدير.
- مكتب السيد مساعد رئيس الجامعة للشؤون العلمية.. للتفضل بالاطلاع.. مع التقدير.
- مكتب السيد مساعد رئيس الجامعة للشؤون الادارية.. للتفضل بالاطلاع.. مع التقدير.
- مكتب السيد معاون العميد للشؤون العلمية في كليتنا.. للتفضل بالاطلاع.. مع التقدير.
- مكتب السيد معاون العميد للشؤون الادارية في كليتنا.. للتفضل بالاطلاع.. مع التقدير.
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ص . ب : 1068 التون كوبري

الاستمارة الاستبائية

معارف واتجاهات الممرضين تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في مستشفى كركوك التعليمي

Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools at Kirkuk Teaching Hospital.

أولاً: المعلومات الديموغرافية

1-الجنس: ذكر انثى

2- العمر: سنة (20-29) سنة (30-39)

سنة (49-40) سنة (50-59)

سنة فأكثر (60)

3- المستوى العلمي: خريج اعدادية معهد كلية عليا

4- الحالة الزوجية : أعزب متزوج مطلق ارمل

5- مدة الخدمة: اقل من (5) سنة (5-9) سنة

(14-10) سنة (15-19) سنة

(24-20) سنة (25) سنة فأكثر

6- القسم:

7- هل اشتركت في دورات حول الذكاء الاصطناعي :

نعم لا

إذا كان الجواب بنعم

مدة الدورة: 1-2يوم 3-5 يوم 6 يوم فأكثر

مكان الدورة: داخل المحافظة خارج المحافظة خارج البلد

Appendix B:

ثانياً: معارف الممرضين تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي:

ت	الفقرات	اعرف	غير متأكد	لا اعرف
1	الذكاء الاصطناعي هو مصطلح يطلق على علم من أحدث علوم الحاسب الآلي			
2	الذكاء الاصطناعي مُصمّم لمحاكاة الوظائف الإدراكية البشرية			
3	الذكاء الاصطناعي يُستخدم حالياً في مجال الرعاية الصحية			
4	الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكنه معالجة المعلومات بسرعة تفوق سرعة البشر بكثير			
5	الذكاء الاصطناعي يعتمد على أنماط البيانات لاتخاذ القرارات			
6	الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكنه تحويل خط يد الطبيب إلى نص رقمي واضح			
7	الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكنه توفير ترجمة فورية للمرضى الذين يتحدثون لغات مختلفة			
8	الذكاء الاصطناعي هو أداة لمساعدة الممرضين، وليس لاستبدالهم بالكامل			
9	توجد حدود ونقاط ضعف في أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي			
10	أنظمة الذكاء الاصطناعي قد ترتكب أخطاء أحياناً أو تقدم مشورة خاطئة			
11	أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي قد تنتج توصيات غير ملائمة ثقافياً أو دينياً بسبب عدم قدرتها على تفسير السياق الاجتماعي والديني			
12	الذكاء الاصطناعي لا يمكنه التعامل مع المعضلات الأخلاقية المعقدة أو قرارات نهاية الحياة مثل البشر			

ثالثاً : اتجاهات الممرضين تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي:

ت	الفقرات	غير موافق بشدة	غير موافق	محايد	موافق	موافق بشدة
1	الذكاء الاصطناعي سيعزز جودة الرعاية التمريضية بشكل كبير					
2	الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكن أن يحسن دقة التشخيص وتخطيط العلاج في الرعاية الصحية					
3	أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكن أن تحسن اتخاذ القرار التمريضي					
4	الذكاء الاصطناعي في التمريض سيؤدي إلى رعاية مرضى أكثر كفاءة وفعالية من حيث التكلفة					
5	الذكاء الاصطناعي يمكن أن يساعد في تقليل عدد الأخطاء الطبية					
6	يجب توفير تدريب وتعليم متخصص حول الذكاء الاصطناعي لجميع الممرضين					
7	الشعور بالارتياح عند استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في مهامه اليومية					
8	الذكاء الاصطناعي سيبتيح للممرضين قضاء وقت أطول في تقديم الرعاية المباشرة للمرضى					
9	استخدام الذكاء الاصطناعي في الرعاية الصحية يجب أن يكون خاضعاً للإشراف					
10	استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي يؤثر سلباً على العلاقة العلاجية بين الممرض والمريض					
11	الذكاء الاصطناعي سيحل محل الممرضين					
12	الذكاء الاصطناعي سيحد من فرص العمل للممرضين الجدد					
13	وجود مخاوف بشأن سرية وخصوصية بيانات المرضى عند المعالجة بالذكاء الاصطناعي					
14	الممرضون مستعدون للتدريب والتعليم المستمر حول استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في الرعاية الصحية					

Appendix C:

قائمة بأسماء الخبراء المحكمين لاستمارة الاستبيان

ت	اسم الخبير	اللقب العلمي	الشهادة	محل العمل	سنوات الخدمة
1	أ.د. سمير سعدون مصطفى	أستاذ	دكتوراه هندسة كهربائية	جامعة الكتاب – الكلية التقنية الهندسية	40 سنة
2	أ.م.د. ابراهيم حسن مصطفى	استاذ مساعد	دكتوراه تمريض	جامعة الكتاب – كلية التمريض	23 سنة
3	م. عدنان رشيد عزيز	مدرس	ماجستير تمريض	جامعة أربيل الطبية – كلية التمريض	20 سنة
4	م.د. كاري ز نامق كاكمرهش	مدرس	دكتوراه تمريض	جامعة الكتاب – كلية التمريض	18 سنة
5	أ.م.د. ياسين احمد محمد	أستاذ مساعد	دكتوراه هندسة حاسبات- ذكاء اصطناعي	جامعة الكتاب – الكلية التقنية الهندسية	12 سنة

الإهداء

ما كان لهذا العمل أن يُنجز لولا توفيق الله ورعايته.

نهدي هذا العمل إلى كل من ألهمنا ودعمنا في كل خطوة وإلى كل من حوّل اللحظات إلى محطات بارزة في المعرفة والتقدم وإلى من غرس فينا الإيمان بأن الوقت ليس مجرد عداد للأيام بل أداة لبناء حياة ومستقبل أفضل.

نهدي هذا البحث إلى عائلاتنا التي كانت مصدر دعمنا الأول والدائم في كل مراحل حياتنا والذين منحونا ثقتهم ووقفوا إلى جانبنا. وإلى كل من ساهم في رسم مسارنا نحو المعرفة.

كما نتقدم بالشكر والتقدير لمشرف البحث على توجيهاته وملاحظاته القيمة ودعمه وتشجيعه ومساعدته في إنجاز هذا العمل.

علاوة على ذلك، نعرب عن شكرنا وتقديرنا العميق لجميع أستاذتنا في كلية التمريض الذين دعمونا وشجعونا خلال فترة الدراسة وإلى الخبراء الذين أثروا هذا البحث بملاحظاتهم ونصائحهم القيمة.

نهدي هذا النجاح لنا ولكل من سعى معنا ولكل من مد لنا يد العون أو دعمنا بكلمة طيبة أو دعاء صادق.

الباحثون

الملخص:

الخلفية: الذكاء الاصطناعي هو علم يهتم بمحاكاة القدرات الإدراكية البشرية من خلال خوارزميات معقدة ولديه القدرة الكاملة على إحداث تحول كبير في مجال ممارسة التمريض.

الأهداف: تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى تقييم معارف الممرضين واتجاهاتهم تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في مستشفى كركوك التعليمي وتحديدتها وفقاً لخصائصهم الديموغرافية.

المنهجية: اعتمدت هذه الدراسة تصميماً وصفيّاً كمياً. أُجريت الدراسة بين 10 تشرين الثاني 2025 و15 آذار 2026، وتم اختيار عينة غير احتمالية (غرضية) من 40 ممرضاً وممرضة يعملون في مستشفى كركوك التعليمي. يتكون الاستبيان من ثلاثة أجزاء: الجزء الأول يتضمن الخصائص الديموغرافية للمشاركين، الجزء الثاني يتضمن معارف الممرضين، والجزء الثالث يتضمن اتجاهات الممرضين تجاه الذكاء الاصطناعي. تم تحليل البيانات باستخدام الإحصاءات الوصفية (التكرارات والنسب المئوية).

الاستنتاجات: خلصت الدراسة إلى أن الغالبية العظمى من الممرضين والممرضات أظهروا معرفة متوسطة واتجاهات محايدة تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي. كما أظهرت الدراسة أن معظم العينة هن إناث ولديهن خبرة أقل من 5 سنوات ويحملن دبلوم تمريض. كما أظهرت أن معظم عينة البحث لم يتلقوا أي تعليم أو دورات تدريبية حول الذكاء الاصطناعي.

التوصيات: توصي الدراسة بتعزيز التعليم المستمر حول أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي وأخلاقياته داخل دائرة صحة كركوك، ودمج الذكاء الاصطناعي في مناهج التمريض، تحديداً في جامعة الكتاب، مع التأكيد على إمكانياته للخير الاجتماعي، وتوسيع الأبحاث المستقبلية من خلال عينات أكبر وأكثر تنوعاً.

وزارة التعليم العالي
والبحث العلمي

جامعة الكتاب
كلية التمريض

معارف واتجاهات الممرضين تجاه استخدام أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في مستشفى كركوك التعليمي

مشروع بحث تخرج
مقدم من قبل:

سيف سعد فلاح
ايمان عرفان عثمان

إلى

كلية التمريض / جامعة الكتاب
وهي جزء من نيل شهادة البكالوريوس
في علوم التمريض

بإشراف:

د. مرغوب حسين ياس